

Assessing the Impact of a Pharmacist-Laboratory-Nurse Team on Optimizing Anemia Management in Hospitalized Patients

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Abstract

Anemia is a prevalent condition among hospitalized patients, negatively impacting recovery time and quality of life. This study aimed to assess the impact of multidisciplinary collaboration involving pharmacists, laboratory specialists, and nurses on anemia management. A mixed-methods approach was used, including quantitative analysis of patient outcomes and qualitative interviews with healthcare professionals. The results demonstrated significant improvements in hemoglobin levels, reduced hospital stay length, and lower readmission rates, indicating the effectiveness of multidisciplinary teamwork. Qualitative findings highlighted the benefits of improved communication and patient-centered care, while also identifying challenges such as time constraints and differing departmental priorities. The study underscores the importance of collaborative care in improving anemia management outcomes.

Keywords: Anemia Management, Multidisciplinary Collaboration, Pharmacists, Laboratory Specialists, Nurses, Patient Outcomes, Hospital Care

Introduction

Anemia is a common clinical condition, particularly in hospitalized patients, that significantly affects patient outcomes, including recovery time and quality of life (Zaninetti et al., 2018). Effective anemia management requires a multidisciplinary approach, integrating multiple healthcare professionals to address the underlying causes, provide appropriate interventions, and ensure close patient monitoring (Bressman et al., 2021). Collaboration between pharmacists, laboratory specialists, and nurses plays a crucial role in optimizing anemia management by ensuring accurate diagnosis, individualized treatment, and continuous evaluation of therapeutic progress.

Pharmacists contribute to anemia management by ensuring appropriate medication use, including the administration of iron supplements, erythropoiesis-stimulating agents, and vitamin therapies (El Nekidy et al., 2020). Their role also includes monitoring drug interactions, patient adherence, and evaluating pharmacotherapy effectiveness. Laboratory specialists, on the other hand, provide essential diagnostic information through the analysis of hemoglobin levels, ferritin, and other hematological parameters critical for determining the type and severity of anemia (Gelaw et al., 2019). These test results inform the choice of treatment interventions, making the laboratory specialist a pivotal member of the care team.

Nurses are vital in implementing the prescribed treatments and providing patient-centered care, including monitoring clinical symptoms, administering medication, and educating patients about anemia and its management (Lukewich et al., 2014). They act as a bridge between the laboratory data, the pharmacist's recommendations, and the patient, ensuring that care is both timely and effective. By working together, pharmacists, laboratory specialists, and nurses can address gaps in care, facilitate rapid adjustments in treatment, and ultimately improve patient outcomes.

This study aims to assess the impact of collaborative management involving pharmacists, laboratory specialists, and nurses on the effectiveness of anemia treatment in hospitalized patients. The goal is to explore how multidisciplinary teamwork can contribute to enhanced diagnostic accuracy, better therapeutic outcomes, and improved quality of life for anemic patients.

Literature Review

Anemia management in hospitalized patients is a complex and multifaceted process that benefits significantly from a multidisciplinary approach. Several studies have highlighted the importance of collaborative care in improving patient outcomes in anemia management. Zaninetti et al. (2018) emphasized that anemia is highly prevalent among hospitalized patients and significantly impacts recovery time, thereby necessitating coordinated interventions from multiple healthcare professionals. Effective management of anemia not only improves clinical outcomes but also enhances the patient's quality of life and reduces hospital stay durations (Zaninetti et al., 2018).

Pharmacists have a critical role in anemia management, particularly in optimizing pharmacotherapy. El Nekidy et al. (2020) demonstrated that pharmacists play an essential role in selecting appropriate medications, such as iron supplements and erythropoiesis-stimulating agents, and ensuring that patients adhere to their treatment regimens. Their involvement in medication counseling and the identification of potential drug interactions is crucial for minimizing adverse effects and enhancing therapeutic outcomes (El Nekidy et al., 2020). Additionally, pharmacists are instrumental in educating patients about their condition and the importance of adherence, which is vital for effective management.

Laboratory specialists contribute by providing the diagnostic backbone for anemia management. According to Gelaw et al. (2019), laboratory testing is essential for determining the type and severity of anemia, which directly influences treatment decisions. Biomarkers such as hemoglobin, ferritin, and transferrin saturation are key in diagnosing anemia and monitoring the effectiveness of interventions. Accurate laboratory diagnostics allow healthcare providers to tailor treatment plans to the patient's specific needs, thereby improving overall management outcomes (Gelaw et al., 2019).

Nurses are also central to the management of anemia, providing direct patient care and serving as the main point of contact between patients and other healthcare professionals. Lukewich et al. (2014) noted that nurses play a crucial role in monitoring patients' clinical symptoms, administering medications, and providing education about anemia and its treatment. Their role in patient education is particularly important, as it empowers patients to take an active role in their treatment, which has been linked to improved adherence and better health outcomes (Lukewich et al., 2014).

The collaboration between pharmacists, laboratory specialists, and nurses has been shown to enhance the quality of anemia management significantly. Bressman et al. (2021) highlighted that a multidisciplinary approach leads to improved diagnostic accuracy, individualized treatment plans, and continuous patient

evaluation, which are all key factors in successful anemia management. By integrating their expertise, healthcare professionals can address the diverse aspects of anemia, from accurate diagnosis to effective treatment and patient education, ultimately improving patient outcomes and quality of life (Bressman et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the importance of effective communication and teamwork among healthcare professionals cannot be overstated. Studies have shown that regular interdisciplinary meetings and clear communication channels contribute to a better understanding of patient needs and more timely adjustments in treatment (Bressman et al., 2021). This collaborative model is essential for managing complex conditions like anemia, where timely intervention and continuous monitoring are critical to preventing complications and ensuring positive outcomes.

In summary, the literature supports the notion that a multidisciplinary approach to anemia management—incorporating pharmacists, laboratory specialists, and nurses—can significantly improve patient outcomes. Each professional brings a unique set of skills that, when combined, provide comprehensive care, from diagnosis and treatment to patient education and monitoring. The present study aims to build on this existing body of knowledge by exploring the specific contributions of each team member in anemia management within a tertiary hospital setting.

Methodology

This study was conducted at a tertiary hospital and employed a mixed-methods approach to assess the impact of multidisciplinary collaboration on anemia management in hospitalized patients. The study included both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the outcomes.

Study Design and Setting

The study took place in a tertiary hospital, involving various wards where anemia management is frequently required, including internal medicine, surgery, and intensive care units. The study was designed as a retrospective observational analysis combined with qualitative interviews of healthcare professionals. The retrospective component focused on reviewing medical records to evaluate patient outcomes, while the qualitative component involved interviews with pharmacists, laboratory specialists, and nurses.

Participants

The study involved hospitalized patients diagnosed with anemia, who were treated between January and December 2023. Patients were included if they were aged 18 years or older and had received care from a multidisciplinary team involving pharmacists, laboratory specialists, and nurses. Healthcare professionals participating in the qualitative interviews included six pharmacists, five laboratory specialists, and eight nurses, all of whom were directly involved in the anemia management process.

Data Collection

Quantitative data were collected from electronic medical records, focusing on clinical parameters such as hemoglobin levels, ferritin, transferrin saturation, and patient outcomes, including length of hospital stay and readmission rates. Data on medication use, dosage adjustments, and adherence were also collected. Patient outcomes were compared before and after the implementation of a formal multidisciplinary collaboration protocol.

Qualitative data were collected through semi-structured interviews with the healthcare professionals involved in anemia management. The interviews explored their experiences with multidisciplinary teamwork, challenges faced, and perceived benefits of the collaborative approach. Interviews were conducted in person, audio-recorded, and transcribed for analysis.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Changes in hemoglobin levels, length of stay, and readmission rates were assessed using paired t-tests to determine the effectiveness of the multidisciplinary approach. The data were analyzed using statistical software, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis. Transcripts were reviewed to identify recurring themes related to the benefits and challenges of multidisciplinary collaboration. Coding was conducted independently by two researchers to ensure reliability, and any discrepancies were resolved through discussion.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the ethics committee before the commencement of the study. Informed consent was obtained from healthcare professionals participating in the interviews. Patient data were anonymized to ensure confidentiality, and all procedures complied with relevant ethical guidelines.

Findings

Quantitative Findings

The quantitative findings revealed significant improvements in patient outcomes following the implementation of the multidisciplinary collaboration protocol.

Parameter	Pre-Intervention Mean (SD)	Post-Intervention Mean (SD)	p-value
Hemoglobin Level (g/dL)	9.5 (1.2)	11.3 (1.1)	< 0.01
Length of Hospital Stay (days)	10.4 (3.1)	8.1 (2.8)	< 0.05
Readmission Rate (%)	15.2	9.8	< 0.05

Table 1 illustrates the improvements in key clinical outcomes. The mean hemoglobin level increased significantly from 9.5 g/dL to 11.3 g/dL ($p < 0.01$), indicating more effective anemia management. Additionally, the average length of hospital stay decreased from 10.4 days to 8.1 days ($p < 0.05$), and the readmission rate dropped from 15.2% to 9.8% ($p < 0.05$), demonstrating enhanced patient recovery and reduced complications.

Qualitative Findings

Thematic analysis of the qualitative interviews identified several key themes and sub-themes related to the benefits and challenges of multidisciplinary collaboration.

Theme 1: Improved Communication and Teamwork

- Sub-theme 1.1: Enhanced Interprofessional Communication

- Participant Quote: "Communication between pharmacists, nurses, and laboratory specialists has improved significantly. We now have regular meetings to discuss patient progress, which has made a big difference in how we manage anemia." (Nurse 3)

- Sub-theme 1.2: Better Understanding of Roles

- Participant Quote: "Understanding each other's roles has helped streamline our workflow. We know who to contact for specific issues, which has reduced delays." (Pharmacist 2)

Theme 2: Patient-Centered Care

- Sub-theme 2.1: Timely Adjustments to Treatment

- Participant Quote: "The laboratory results are communicated quickly, allowing us to make timely adjustments to treatment. This has had a positive impact on patient outcomes." (Laboratory Specialist 1)

- Sub-theme 2.2: Improved Patient Education

- Participant Quote: "Patients are now more informed about their condition and treatment. The educational materials provided by pharmacists and nurses have really empowered patients." (Nurse 5)

Theme 3: Challenges in Multidisciplinary Collaboration

- Sub-theme 3.1: Time Constraints

- Participant Quote: "Finding the time for regular team meetings can be challenging, especially with our workload. However, we see the benefits, so we try to make it work." (Pharmacist 4)

- Sub-theme 3.2: Differing Priorities

- Participant Quote: "Sometimes the priorities of different departments don't align, which can create friction. We've been working on aligning our goals better." (Laboratory Specialist 3)

Discussion

The findings of this study demonstrate that multidisciplinary collaboration significantly enhances the management of anemia in hospitalized patients, leading to improved clinical outcomes. The quantitative results indicate that the implementation of a formal multidisciplinary collaboration protocol resulted in significant improvements in hemoglobin levels, reduced length of hospital stay, and a lower readmission rate. These findings align with previous research that has highlighted the importance of integrating the expertise of different healthcare professionals to optimize patient care (Zaninetti et al., 2018; Bressman et al., 2021).

The increase in hemoglobin levels and reduction in hospital stay can be attributed to the timely adjustments in treatment facilitated by better communication between pharmacists, laboratory specialists, and nurses. The prompt sharing of laboratory results enabled pharmacists to adjust medications appropriately, while nurses ensured that patients received timely care and education regarding their treatment. This comprehensive approach ensured that patients received individualized care, which has been shown to be more effective in managing anemia (Gelaw et al., 2019).

The reduction in readmission rates is another notable outcome of this study. By addressing anemia more effectively during the initial hospital stay, patients were less likely to experience complications requiring readmission. The qualitative findings support this, with healthcare professionals emphasizing the importance of communication and teamwork in providing patient-centered care. Regular interdisciplinary meetings and role clarity were identified as key components of successful collaboration, which contributed to improved patient monitoring and timely interventions (Lukewich et al., 2014).

Despite the positive outcomes, challenges in multidisciplinary collaboration were also identified. Time constraints and differing departmental priorities were highlighted as barriers to effective teamwork. These challenges are consistent with findings from other studies, which have noted that the workload of healthcare professionals can hinder regular interdisciplinary communication (Bressman et al., 2021). Addressing these challenges will be crucial for sustaining and further improving the quality of care. Strategies such as dedicated time for interdisciplinary meetings and aligning departmental goals could help mitigate these barriers and enhance the effectiveness of the collaborative model.

The qualitative findings also underscored the importance of patient education in anemia management. Nurses and pharmacists played a pivotal role in educating patients about their condition and treatment options, empowering them to take an active role in their care. This empowerment is linked to better treatment adherence and overall outcomes, as patients who understand their treatment are more likely to follow recommendations (El Nekidy et al., 2020).

Overall, the study highlights the value of a multidisciplinary approach in managing anemia in hospitalized patients. The combination of pharmacists' expertise in pharmacotherapy, laboratory specialists' diagnostic capabilities, and nurses' direct patient care and education resulted in a more effective management strategy. Future research should focus on exploring ways to overcome the challenges identified, particularly those related to time constraints and departmental priorities, to further enhance multidisciplinary collaboration.

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